

Standard Potentials of the Silver/Silver Chloride Electrode at different Temperatures and related Thermodynamic Quantities in Ethanol-Water Media

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The standard molal potentials (E_m^0) of the cells of the type,

at five temperatures in the range 15–35° have been determined in ethanol-water media. The E_m^0 values as a function of Celsius temperature t in different solvent compositions have been calculated based on the equation,

$$E_m^0 = a^\circ + b^\circ(t - 25) + c^\circ(t - 25)^2$$

The values of a° , b° and c° have been calculated by least-square method.

The related thermodynamic quantities have been calculated. The dependence of standard potentials at 25° on the dielectric constant of the media (in the light of Born equation), the volume fraction (ϕ_w) and the mole fraction (N_w) of water (based on Feakins-French relationship) have been examined. The variation of thermodynamic quantities ΔG° , ΔS° and ΔH° with various parameters associated with solvent media at 25° has been examined. The mean activity coefficient of hydrochloric acid has been calculated.

THE properties of hydrochloric acid in aqueous organic mixed solvents have long been a subject of interest. The standard potentials of silver/silver chloride electrode in 10 and 20 mass % ethanol at 0, 10, 20, 30 and 45° were determined by Patterson and Felsing¹. Harned and Allen² extended the work to 30, 40 and 50 mass % ethanol, likewise Oiwa³ determined the standard potential in 30, 50, 70 and 90 mass % of ethanol at several temperatures in the range 10–40°. A critical summary of data over the entire range of composition has been given by Feakins and French⁴, standard potentials in 10, 20 and 40 mass % of ethanol in ethanol-water media have been determined by Sankar and coworkers⁵ at 25, 0 and –10°. In the present communication we have determined the standard electrode potential of silver-silver chloride electrodes in 10, 20, 30, 45, 60 and 75 mass % of ethanol in ethanol-water media, at 15, 20, 25, 30 and 35°. In all earlier work as in present study, the cell without liquid junction was used,

Experimental

Ethanol was purified using standard procedure^{6,7}. Hydrochloric acid (A.R.) was purified by distilling it with stannous chloride and the distillate redistilled with double-distilled water to get constant boiling

mixture of hydrochloric acid. Double-distilled water was used throughout. The solvent mixtures of various percentage were always freshly prepared.

Silver-silver chloride electrodes used were of thermal electrolyte type and prepared by the recommended method⁸. The hydrogen electrode consisted of a platinum foil (0.05 mm × 1 cm²). The methods of preparation of platinum chloride solution and platinisation of hydrogen electrode were made following the reported methods⁹. The hydrogen gas (Indian Oxygen) for hydrogen electrode was purified¹⁰.

All the measurements were taken with two silver-silver chloride electrodes and two hydrogen electrodes for each solution. The equilibrium was reached in 3–4 h after the initiation of hydrogen bubbling. The criterion for equilibrium was a stable reading within ±0.05 mV over 0.5 h period. The e.m.f. measurements were made at five different temperatures 15, 20, 25, 30 and 35° with a Leeds-Northrup K₂ potentiometer and galvanometer. The cell e.m.f. values being measured first from 25 to 35° and then from 15 to 25°. The e.m.f. values at 25° at the first and at last were in good agreement (0.1 mV). The e.m.f. readings were corrected to that for the standard 1 atm pressure of hydrogen using the expression⁸,

$$\Delta E = \frac{2.303 RT}{2F} \log \frac{760}{P - P_s}$$

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where, P is barometric pressure and P_s the vapour pressure of the solvent. The vapour pressure values of ethanol-water systems at different temperatures and different compositions were determined by graphical interpolation¹¹ using the data from Landolt-Bornstein tables. The dielectric constants (D) of mixed solvents at each celsius temperature was calculated by using Akerlof¹² equation. The corrected e.m.f. values for the cell (Table 1) are the average of four sets.

Results and Discussion

The e.m.f. of the cell is related to the concentration of hydrogen ion m_{H^+} and that of chloride ion m_{Cl^-} , by equation (1),

$$E = E^0 - \frac{RT}{F} \ln m_{H^+} m_{Cl^-} \gamma_{H^+} \gamma_{Cl^-} \quad (1)$$

$$= E^0 - 2RT/F \ln m \gamma_{\pm}$$

where E^0 is the standard potential of Ag, AgCl electrode, γ_{H^+} and γ_{Cl^-} are the activity coefficients of hydrogen and chloride ions respectively, m is the molality of hydrochloric acid and $\gamma_{\pm}$ the mean activity coefficient. This equation can be written in the form,

$$E = E^0 - 2K \log m + \frac{2KA m^{1/2}}{1 + a^0 B m^{1/2}} - c'm + 2K \log (1 + 0.002 M_{xy} m) \quad (2)$$

or

$$E + 2K \log m - \frac{2KA m^{1/2}}{1 + a^0 B m^{1/2}} - 2K \log (1 + 0.002 M_{xy} m) = E^0 - c'm \quad (3)$$

where $K = RT \ln 10/F$, A and B are Debye-Hückel constants, a^0 is the ion size parameter ($\text{\AA}$) and M_{xy} the molecular weight of the mixed solvent. Equation (3) reduces to

$$E^0 = E_m^0 - bm \quad (4)$$

where m is molal concentration and b the constant. The values of E^0 are plotted against m to get the standard electrode potential in molality scale. E_m^0 has also been determined by least-square method. Graphical values are in good agreement with the least-square values. The values of E_m^0 against different mass % of ethanol at different temperature is recorded in Table 2. E_m^0 at different temperature for any mixed medium (mass %) may be written as,

$$E_m^0 = a^0 + b^0 (t - 25) + c^0 (t - 25)^2 \quad (5)$$

The values of a^0 , b^0 and c^0 have been determined by least-square method. These values are given in Table 3.

The standard free energy change (ΔG^0), enthalpy change (ΔH^0) and entropy change (ΔS^0)

TABLE 1—E.m.f. VALUES OF THE CELL CORRECTED TO 1 atm PRESSURE OF H_2 AT DIFFERENT TEMPERATURES

Strength mmol kg ⁻¹	$E(V)$				
	15°	20°	25°	30°	35°
10% Ethanol					
0.105 34	0.343 57	0.343 31	0.343 19	0.341 43	0.341 52
0.094 01	0.349 27	0.349 28	0.349 69	0.347 51	0.347 52
0.082 95	0.353 83	0.353 60	0.353 80	0.353 95	0.353 57
0.071 70	0.361 33	0.361 71	0.362 11	0.361 09	0.361 31
0.066 31	0.365 29	0.365 42	0.366 01	0.365 27	0.364 76
0.060 66	0.369 09	0.369 52	0.370 09	0.369 81	0.369 63
0.049 14	0.378 90	0.379 14	0.380 21	0.379 13	0.379 39
0.043 49	0.384 77	0.385 34	0.386 24	0.385 14	0.385 65
0.032 18	0.398 42	0.399 15	0.400 01	0.399 86	0.400 15
0.026 53	0.407 37	0.408 36	0.409 53	0.408 44	0.410 33
0.015 62	0.432 26	0.433 54	0.435 15	0.435 49	0.436 44
20% Ethanol					
0.090 47	0.348 96	0.345 29	0.345 03	0.343 68	0.343 89
0.085 09	0.346 69	0.347 77	0.347 69	0.346 33	0.346 21
0.073 91	0.352 76	0.353 91	0.353 76	0.353 07	0.353 48
0.063 10	0.360 38	0.361 68	0.361 64	0.361 72	0.361 26
0.045 26	0.375 37	0.376 98	0.377 03	0.377 75	0.377 67
0.039 10	0.382 66	0.384 42	0.384 63	0.384 78	0.384 62
0.033 46	0.389 38	0.391 04	0.391 86	0.391 56	0.392 51
0.028 98	0.396 05	0.398 17	0.398 60	0.398 72	0.399 11
0.023 36	0.406 72	0.408 90	0.409 54	0.409 61	0.410 13
0.011 91	0.437 63	0.440 47	0.441 39	0.441 93	0.444 13
30% Ethanol					
0.103 75	0.330 94	0.332 11	0.332 35	0.329 73	0.326 75
0.093 36	0.335 65	0.336 93	0.338 33	0.334 41	0.331 45
0.080 58	0.342 97	0.344 09	0.345 42	0.341 55	0.338 78
0.070 22	0.348 94	0.349 93	0.351 32	0.348 25	0.345 61
0.059 77	0.356 05	0.357 40	0.359 60	0.355 80	0.353 22
0.049 41	0.364 61	0.366 29	0.368 33	0.364 94	0.362 53
0.039 43	0.375 08	0.376 63	0.379 63	0.376 05	0.373 92
0.017 86	0.411 72	0.414 01	0.416 61	0.414 20	0.412 68
0.012 62	0.427 56	0.430 16	0.433 62	0.431 04	0.429 56
0.006 79	0.456 51	0.459 74	0.463 39	0.461 36	0.460 76
45% Ethanol					
0.102 67	0.328 30	0.329 11	0.326 25	0.323 45	0.321 32
0.092 21	0.332 44	0.333 05	0.330 23	0.327 56	0.325 50
0.083 08	0.337 68	0.338 56	0.335 92	0.333 29	0.331 33
0.071 36	0.344 30	0.345 37	0.342 85	0.340 44	0.338 67
0.060 96	0.350 98	0.351 97	0.349 47	0.347 09	0.345 42
0.049 30	0.360 01	0.361 11	0.358 96	0.356 74	0.355 23
0.037 64	0.372 79	0.374 31	0.372 41	0.370 51	0.369 28
0.025 86	0.389 05	0.390 76	0.389 03	0.387 30	0.386 34
0.020 13	0.400 39	0.402 65	0.401 03	0.399 69	0.398 96
60% Ethanol					
0.098 62	0.319 28	0.317 66	0.314 97	0.316 18	0.314 03
0.087 29	0.325 13	0.324 26	0.320 92	0.321 57	0.318 84
0.076 35	0.331 33	0.330 21	0.327 47	0.327 56	0.325 24
0.064 98	0.338 18	0.337 46	0.334 57	0.333 65	0.333 70
0.051 00	0.348 68	0.347 86	0.345 72	0.346 55	0.344 06
0.038 59	0.361 33	0.361 31	0.358 79	0.360 03	0.357 66
0.026 05	0.379 03	0.378 51	0.377 32	0.378 27	0.375 61
0.013 64	0.408 71	0.408 56	0.407 02	0.408 91	0.406 42
0.009 20	0.427 33	0.426 95	0.426 37	0.427 93	0.425 53
75% Ethanol					
0.100 50	0.300 15	0.298 53	0.296 00	0.292 02	0.289 50
0.089 05	0.305 05	0.303 53	0.301 00	0.297 57	0.294 67
0.083 13	0.308 95	0.306 03	0.304 10	0.300 92	0.297 87
0.071 17	0.314 10	0.313 43	0.310 50	0.307 92	0.304 47
0.059 65	0.322 55	0.320 53	0.318 25	0.316 27	0.314 92
0.047 75	0.333 05	0.331 63	0.328 60	0.325 52	0.324 42
0.035 64	0.344 65	0.344 53	0.341 30	0.338 12	0.337 27
0.023 60	0.362 55	0.363 23	0.360 50	0.359 32	0.357 37
0.011 52	0.393 52	0.394 73	0.393 40	0.391 52	0.389 62

TABLE 2—VALUES OF E_m^0 OF Ag-AgCl ELECTRODE AT DIFFERENT TEMPERATURES IN ETHANOL-WATER MEDIA

EtOH Mass %	E_m^0 (V)				
	15°	20°	25°	30°	35°
10	0.219 11 ±0.000 18	0.216 79 ±0.000 24	0.214 69 ±0.000 30	0.211 02 ±0.000 30	0.208 50 ±0.000 18
20	0.211 12 ±0.000 18	0.209 83 ±0.000 18	0.206 97 ±0.000 27	0.203 84 ±0.000 27	0.201 17 ±0.000 18
30	0.202 77 ±0.000 12	0.201 36 ±0.000 12	0.200 76 ±0.000 18	0.194 23 ±0.000 12	0.188 97 ±0.000 12
45	0.194 81 ±0.000 21	0.193 07 ±0.000 27	0.187 89 ±0.000 27	0.182 70 ±0.000 27	0.178 27 ±0.000 27
60	0.183 20 ±0.000 48	0.179 02 ±0.000 39	0.173 48 ±0.000 27	0.170 80 ±0.000 27	0.168 97 ±0.000 27
75	0.156 18 ±0.000 33	0.152 94 ±0.000 39	0.145 93 ±0.000 48	0.140 89 ±0.000 48	0.135 05 ±0.000 48

TABLE 3—VALUES OF THE CONSTANTS OF EQUATION (5)

EtOH Mass %	a_0	$b_0 \times 10^{-4}$	$c_0 \times 10^{-6}$
20	0.207 02	5.178	8.657
30	0.199 57	6.946	38.942
45	0.188 12	8.690	15.400
60	0.174 11	9.386	2.686
75	0.146 68	10.862	9.514

TABLE 5—ACTIVITY COEFFICIENT ($\gamma_{\pm}$) OF HCl IN EtOH-H₂O MEDIA AT DIFFERENT TEMPERATURES

EtOH Mass %	m mol kg ⁻¹	$\gamma_{\pm}$				
		15°	20°	25°	30°	35°
10	0.094 01	0.774	0.773	0.769	0.780	0.776
	0.060 66	0.804	0.802	0.801	0.789	0.793
	0.049 14	0.815	0.818	0.812	0.815	0.815
	0.032 18	0.840	0.841	0.844	0.837	0.842
	0.015 62	0.876	0.877	0.877	0.872	0.876
20	0.090 47	0.762	0.757	0.752	0.760	0.752
	0.063 10	0.785	0.785	0.781	0.772	0.778
	0.045 26	0.809	0.808	0.806	0.795	0.796
	0.033 46	0.825	0.828	0.818	0.822	0.814
	0.011 91	0.878	0.874	0.877	0.880	0.866
30	0.093 86	0.738	0.732	0.736	0.732	0.732
	0.069 77	0.764	0.762	0.760	0.759	0.759
	0.049 41	0.778	0.773	0.776	0.771	0.771
	0.039 43	0.789	0.790	0.782	0.781	0.779
	0.012 62	0.857	0.855	0.853	0.852	0.854
45	0.092 21	0.679	0.679	0.679	0.678	0.678
	0.060 96	0.707	0.706	0.707	0.705	0.705
	0.049 30	0.729	0.729	0.727	0.725	0.724
	0.037 64	0.738	0.735	0.733	0.730	0.723
	0.020 13	0.791	0.784	0.784	0.781	0.779
60	0.098 62	0.655	0.652	0.646	0.627	0.601
	0.064 98	0.679	0.669	0.669	0.647	0.630
	0.051 00	0.700	0.694	0.687	0.678	0.660
	0.038 59	0.710	0.702	0.704	0.693	0.676
	0.013 64	0.782	0.780	0.779	0.769	0.763
75	0.089 05	0.560	0.570	0.550	0.560	0.556
	0.059 65	0.588	0.608	0.587	0.584	0.567
	0.047 75	0.595	0.610	0.599	0.611	0.592
	0.023 60	0.664	0.670	0.651	0.641	0.644
	0.011 52	0.729	0.725	0.704	0.716	0.719

for the reaction in ethanol-water media, were calculated from the relations,

$$\Delta G^0 = -nFE_m^0 \quad (9)$$

$$\Delta H^0 = -nF \left[E_m^0 - T \left(\frac{d E_m^0}{dT} \right)_P \right] \quad (10)$$

$$\Delta S^0 = \frac{\Delta H^0 - \Delta G^0}{T} \quad (11)$$

and the values are given in Table 4.

TABLE 4—VALUES OF DERIVED THERMODYNAMIC QUANTITIES FOR THE CELL REACTION $1/2 H_2(g) + AgCl(s) \rightleftharpoons H^+ + Ag(s) + Cl^-$ AT 25° IN EtOH-H₂O MEDIA

EtOH Mass %	ΔG^0 (kJ mol ⁻¹)			ΔH^0 (kJ mol ⁻¹)			ΔS^0 JK ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹		
	25°	25°	25°	25°	25°	25°	25°	25°	25°
10	-20.718 ±0.018	-36.249 ±0.120	-52.1 ±0.3	-19.978 ±0.027	-34.871 ±0.120	-50.0 ±0.3	-19.373 ±0.018	-39.359 ±0.030	-67.0 ±0.3
20	-19.978 ±0.027	-34.871 ±0.120	-50.0 ±0.3	-18.131 ±0.027	-43.135 ±0.110	-83.9 ±0.3	-19.373 ±0.018	-39.359 ±0.030	-67.0 ±0.3
30	-19.373 ±0.018	-39.359 ±0.030	-67.0 ±0.3	-16.741 ±0.027	-43.603 ±0.110	-90.1 ±0.3	-18.131 ±0.027	-43.135 ±0.110	-83.9 ±0.3
45	-18.131 ±0.027	-43.135 ±0.110	-83.9 ±0.3	-16.741 ±0.027	-43.603 ±0.110	-90.1 ±0.3	-16.741 ±0.027	-43.603 ±0.110	-90.1 ±0.3
60	-16.741 ±0.027	-43.603 ±0.110	-90.1 ±0.3	-14.087 ±0.048	-45.340 ±0.200	-104.8 ±0.3	-14.087 ±0.027	-45.340 ±0.110	-104.8 ±0.3
75	-14.087 ±0.048	-45.340 ±0.200	-104.8 ±0.3						

The mean activity coefficient values ($\gamma_{\pm}$) of hydrochloric acid in ethanol-water mixtures at 15, 20, 25, 30 and 35° were evaluated by equation,

$$-\log \gamma_{\pm} = \frac{E - E_m^0}{2K} + \log m \quad (12)$$

and the values are tabulated in Table 5.

E_m^0 was plotted against $1/D$ (Born plot). The standard deviation for the plot has been found to be 6.7 mV. Similar observation was also observed by Oiwa¹³ for Ag | AgCl electrode in methanol-water, Banerjee and coworkers¹⁴ for Ag | AgBr electrode in ethylene glycol-water and Basu and Aditya¹⁵ for Hg | Hg₂(OAc)₂ electrode in dioxane water media. The deviation from linearity indicates interaction of the organic components of the solvent with the ions or the second components participation as the proportion of this becomes larger.

Fig. 1. Plots of ΔG , ΔS and ΔH against $1/D$.

ΔH° , ΔG° and ΔS° for the reaction at 25° were plotted against $1/D$ (Fig. 1). It is seen from the plots that the enthalpy increases as the mass % of ethanol increases and reaches maximum at around 20–30% ethanol and then gradually decreases. Same behaviour is also observed in case of the entropy change.

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